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A DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS ON THE GENDER ISSUES IN TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to examine the gender issues in physical education instruction at several state colleges and university schools in the Philippines. Utilizing descriptive research, data revealed that physical education teachers need to work on delivering subject matter, planning lessons, and developing didactics in a way that is more gender sensitive. More information demonstrated that physical education teachers lacked the education required to discuss gender concepts, regulations, and standards as well as development approaches in instructing physical education. It is advised that gender equality tools, learning resources, and knowledge products be produced and made accessible for usage in the classroom and coaching context in order to increase gender sensitivity in the teaching of physical education. Physical education instructors are also invited to take part in gender and development training to increase their understanding of gender issues and their capacity to give instruction that is gender sensitive.

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INTRODUCTION

Numerous studies have been conducted to look at gender-sensitive practices in physical education and sports. Parri and Cecilian, 2019; Donnelly et al., 2013 The lack of a useful tool to measure gender-sensitive instruction among teachers has emerged as an issue in the investigations of delivery and the curricula, among other important findings including sexist behaviors were found in the channel of communication, the students chosen for demonstrations, task organization, and the lack of a tool. Research that considers gender as a significant variable in environmental and development studies is considered to be gender sensitive. Gender sensitive research does not exclusively focus on women or on gender relationships. The roles that men and women play have varied effects on the environment and development. Furthermore, the power dynamics between men and women have a significant impact on how men and women view environmental and development issues. Therefore, gender sensitive research gives equal weight to both the similarities and differences between men's and women's experiences and points of view. (Mortejo et al., 2022; del Castillo Andrés et al., 2012) Only recently has gender been acknowledged as a significant research variable. Though it is beginning to gain acceptance in the social sciences, it is rarely acknowledged and used in the natural sciences, economics, or other disciplines. In order to paint a fuller picture of the issue, it offers fresh viewpoints, poses fresh issues, and makes use of fresh analytical techniques. Men and women can have quite different viewpoints on a subject because they have distinct positions and levels of influence. They could better understand the issues by fusing their various perspectives and experiences. As a result, incorporating a gender perspective can increase relevance, coverage, and quality (ADEA Working Group on Higher Education

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2006), as men and women play different roles and may be affected in different ways by their respective social statuses and power dynamics, particularly in the academic setting.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a descriptive type of research since its objective was to describe, measure, and analyze data in order to learn the data starting with the quantitative. A select group of physical education instructors from Philippine state universities and colleges participated in the assessment. For at least five years, respondents had to have taught physical education while also coaching in order to be eligible for the study. A self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data in order to assess the gender practices in physical education teaching.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Average Responses' Evaluations of Gender-Sensitive Coaching and Teaching Techniques in the Delivery of the Training Program's Content.

Delivery of the Subject Matter and Training program	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
1. Ensures that the relation between teaching content and gender is revealed	1.79	0.17	Not Gender-Sensitive
2. Sees to it that students reflect about gender-related structural dependencies/constraints within their domain, work environment, and job market	4.06	0.66	Somehow
3. Ensures that both male and female authors and researchers are considered as my reference	4.35	0.70	Not gender sensitive
4. Reinforces topics on gender issues in my lesson (e.g., VAWC, women's right, etc.)	4.06	0.66	Not gender sensitive
5. Adjust my lesson content taking into consideration my male and female students' maturity, prior experiences, and social value	4.29	0.77	Not gender sensitive
6. Presents the subject matter which can be easily learned through optimal replacement, appropriate organization, and sequencing of contents	4.24	0.75	Somehow
7. Develops objectives considering cultural aspects and gender dimensions	4.29	0.77	Not gender sensitive
8. Detects and counter-acts one-sided content and objectives	4.24	0.66	Not gender sensitive
9. Selects content/that will help the learners attain maximum self-sufficiency in learning	4.41	0.62	Not gender sensitive
10. Check and verifies regularly the content to determine if it is within the context of the existing reality about the role of male and female in a society and government.	4.12	0.78	Not Gender-Sensitive

Composite Mean	4.21	0.71	Not Gender-Sensitive
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*Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Highly Gender-Sensitive; 3.40 – 4.19 Very Gender-Sensitive; 2.60 – 3.39 Gender-Sensitive; 1.80– 2.59 Gender-Sensitive Somehow; 1.00 – 1.79 Not Gender-Sensitive.

It is essential for subject matter instructors to become gender sensitive in how they teach their subjects in order to provide a welcoming and fair learning environment and attain gender equality in physical education classrooms (Kriová and Polánková, 2020). The usefulness of methodological and theoretical support in the classroom and in the sporting environment is well understood by PE instructors and sports coaches, especially when teaching or conducting training on gender issues among athletes. By adding a variety of gender viewpoints in the subject matter delivery, where equality in gender is respected and valued, they are actually giving their students and athletes new perspectives on their PE courses (Advincula and Cayabat, 2020).

On the other hand, ensuring the relationship between teaching material and gender is particularly gender sensitive, as evidenced by the mean of the participants' teaching practices. 4.01 with a 0.71 SD. PE teachers' unique practice needs a little more attention, in addition to other things like reflection on gender-related structural dependencies/constraints within their field, workplace, and job market, reinforcing topics on gender issues in the lesson, and regularly checking and verifying the lesson content to see if it is within the context of the current reality about gender roles. The importance of including gender views in the teaching content of PE courses may support the learning of male and female students equally by eliminating the inadvertent and implicit transmission of gender prejudice in the lesson content (Nikoleyczik, 2009). In order to ensure that their classes in PE or any other sports-related courses include appropriate gender views and are generally gender aware, PE teachers and sports coaches must be trained in pertinent educational strategies that can be used to address diversity and diverse points of view, especially when incorporating these strategies into lesson plans (Leathwood and Read, 2009).

Table 2. Mean of Respondents' Ratings on Gender-Sensitive Coaching and Teaching Practices in Terms of How Learning and Coaching Experiences are Organized.

Organization of the Learning Experience	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
1. Uses gender neutral spoken language during discussions in sports and physical education	1.29	0.077	Not Gender-Sensitive
2. Utilizes examples of gender inequity in my lesson and training program and clearly explain these issues in class	1.53	0.062	Not Gender-Sensitive
3. Discusses and analyzes sexist advertising images and the media's representation of men and women in sports	1.18	0.064	Not Gender-Sensitive
4. Presents in the learning/instructional materials (e.g., photos, examples,) at the same hierarchical levels and in non-stereotypic roles	1.29	0.805	Not Gender-Sensitive
5. Gives exercises which address for both men and women to explain their thinking and reasoning	1.35	0.070	Not Gender-Sensitive
6. Challenges traditional male and female stereotypes when giving examples to students (e.g., a female swimmer or a male athlete)	1.89	0.77	Somehow
7. Prioritizes learning styles of my male and female students in the choice of the teaching method	1.29	0.069	Not Gender-Sensitive
8. Utilizes gender neutral language in all my course syllabus in physical education and sports.	1.65	0.0	Not Gender-Sensitive

		61	
9. Initiates exploratory classroom activities following the prescribed guidelines of CHED and other agencies to facilitate gender mainstreaming	1.35	0.070	Not Gender-Sensitive
10. Examines all instructional materials in physical education and sports whethertextbooks, handouts, or workbooks to determine if they are gender biased, gender neutral or gender-sensitive.	1.18	0.073	Not Gender-Sensitive
Composite Mean	1.34	0.071	Not Gender-Sensitive

*Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Highly Gender-Sensitive; 3.40 – 4.19 Very Gender-Sensitive; 2.60 – 3.39 Gender-Sensitive; 1.80– 2.59 Gender-Sensitive Somehow; 1.00 – 1.79 Not Gender-Sensitive

According to the composite mean of 1.34 and SD of 0.71, the teaching methods of physical education faculty members are generally very insensitive to gender in terms of how learning experiences are organized. It supports the findings of the study by Nizeyimana et al. (2022) that teachers are sensitive to gender issues in their classroom activities because they believe that it has a significant impact on instruction. As a result, they were able to plan gender-sensitive learning experiences thanks to the PE teachers' ability to enable gender mainstreaming. Teachers are encouraged to contextualize and localize learning activities as well as encourage the use of inclusive language, uplifting visuals, and messages in order to adopt gender-sensitive learning experiences (Talon and Carreon, 2020). Because of this, PE teachers are careful to design and carry out learning activities that cater to the requirements, interests, and intelligence of both male and female students.

For instance, the use of gender-neutral language by the participants in all of their course syllabi obtained the highest mean of 4.65 and SD of 0.61. Because the use of gender-neutral language in instruction increases students' individual potentials in roles that are not stereotypical, this indicates that the teachers are highly gender-sensitive (Tokas, 2014). The results also supported the findings of Andres et al. (2014), who found that using gender-neutral terminology in training increases gender equality and discourages prejudice. Gender-neutral language use serves as a reflection of a society's commitment to the principle of gender equality as well as a tool for swaying public opinion (Semin, 2004). The rejection of generalized masculine words is essential for gender-neutral language, notably in the teaching responsibilities of PE teachers. Despite advancements in PE research and curriculum that are meant to engage females in PE, gender difficulties in PE classes still exist in some schools. The need for PE teachers to be more gender-sensitive in organizing their learning experiences will be able to address these issues (Murphy, Dionigi, and Litchfield, 2014). sensitivity to gender.

The least-rated items, which had a mean of 4.18 and SD values of 0.64 and 0.73, focused on the discussion and analysis of sexist advertising images, the portrayal of men and women in the media, and the assessment of all instructional materials, including textbooks, handouts, and workbooks, to determine whether they are biased against men or women, gender neutral, or sensitive to gender issues. The study by Korenius (2018) also emphasized the need for teachers interested in expanding their pedagogy toward gender sensitivity to effectively employ language and instructional tools. Instructional materials are crucial for teaching students about gender roles and social values in addition to conveying knowledge (Bombani, 2015). Therefore, PE teachers should be aware of any gender stereotypes they may have and have a clear understanding of gender-sensitive education before developing a new set of teaching resources.

Table 3. Mean of Respondents' Assessment on the Gender-Sensitive Teaching and coaching Practices in terms of Organization of Design of Didactic Strategies.

Design of Didactic Strategies	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
1. Helps promote gender equality and sensitivity inside the classroom through giving equally intensive and constructive feedback to male and female students	1.12	0.62	Not Gender-Sensitive
2. Makes a seating plan that supports equal participation regardless of their sex	1.18	0.81	Not Gender-Sensitive
3. Looks at my male and female learners as unique individuals, and not through gender-based perspectives	1.53	0.62	Not Gender-Sensitive
4. Avoids interacting to students who only sits in front of the class to ensure equal participation	1.24	0.90	Not Gender-Sensitive
5. Gives all students the opportunity to take part in class by doing some activities in small groups of three to four students	1.41	0.62	Not Gender-Sensitive
6. Addresses male and female students equally and with similar stimulating demands	1.87	0.62	Somehow
7. Establishes a set of rules with my students from the very beginning to promote ownership	1.24	0.66	Not Gender-Sensitive
8. Calls on or talk to both female and male students in a balanced way	1.47	0.62	Not Gender-Sensitive
9. Provides enough time for my male and female students to answer a question at least four to five seconds	1.35	0.86	Not Gender-Sensitive
10. Encourages students to engage in activities that may help them step outside their gender's comfort-zones (e.g. sports)	1.87	0.62	Somehow
Composite Mean	1.38	0.07	Not Gender-Sensitive

*Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Highly Gender-Sensitive; 3.40 – 4.19 Very Gender-Sensitive; 2.60 – 3.39 Gender-Sensitive; 1.80– 2.59 Gender-Sensitive Somehow; 1.00 – 1.79 Not Gender-Sensitive

The chart also shows that the majority of the questions about the organization and design of didactic techniques, as well as gender-sensitive practices in teaching, were regarded as not being gender-sensitive. Physical education teachers should be aware that the didactic strategies they develop are actually instruments that can be used to reflect on and apply teaching and learning in the real world (Bolondi, Ferretti, and Giberti, 2018). According to Gindl and Hefler (2006), gender-sensitive didactics are genuinely used to recognize and critique gender hierarchies, to enable gender violations, and to accept gender ambivalences. It also attempts to meet the needs and competencies of the students by

giving them equal opportunity to benefit from learning opportunities and designing learning opportunities that do not conceal gender but instead allow participants the chance to advance their gender competences (Srivastava, 2012).

The PE Teachers gave the practice of creating a seating plan that encourages equal participation regardless of a student's gender the lowest mean rating (1.38 and SD = 0.07). This is because seat plans are rarely employed in courses, particularly in higher education settings where the majority of the classes are heterogeneous. The teacher's ignorance of the function of a seating layout in promoting gender sensitivity is another contributing element. Because seating arrangements have the potential to help prevent problem behaviors that reduce student attention and reduce available instructional time, PE teachers should be aware that they are significant classroom setting events (Wannarka and Ruhl, 2008). The seating arrangement in the classroom should be determined by the nature of the academic task and the intended style of conduct. It encourages gender inclusion in a classroom with diverse student populations (Salend, 1998). Therefore, PE instructors should get comfortable creating seating arrangements because doing so will enable them to promote gender inclusivity in the classroom.

Developing instructional resources that are gender-sensitive requires careful consideration of visual representations, claim Anderson, Hussenius, and Gustafsson (2009). Stereotypes must be avoided in favor of a gender depiction that is fairly balanced. When examples and themes are more useful and have a purpose, gender-sensitive educational materials are more effective and appealing to both male and female learners. Participant No. 3 agrees that using gender-sensitive educational materials will contribute in the eradication of gender stereotypes.

CONCLUSION

Physical education instructors and sports coaches must continue their gender-sensitivity training to guarantee that they are gender-neutral. They must also improve their knowledge of gender roles, laws, regulations, policies, and tools for promoting gender equality among physical education teachers and sports coaches. Encouraging them to produce knowledge-based products that may be used in classrooms, gender-neutral educational materials, and other resources. Gender audits of the Physical Education curricula, training program, and materials should be conducted in order to examine and modify these documents to better suit the needs of Physical Education teachers and students. The delivery of physical education and sports education curricula and instruction at various levels of educational sports programs should be evaluated in future research.

Teacher coaches must prioritize the creation of instructional materials for PE courses and training programs since they are effective tools for improving student academic performance and winning performance. The instructional materials used in PE classes and training program must go through constant evaluation in order to study gender-sensitive notions on its main goals, principles, lesson design, and assessment techniques. The effective use of language and teaching resources have significant positive effects on gender equality in the classroom.

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